

Assessing Open Access Friendliness of India Top 10 Management Institutions: A Data Carpentry Approach

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Abstract: *In the current study, the open access friendliness of the top 10 management institutions in India that have been ranked by the National Institutional Ranking Framework of India for 2024 is examined. Open access friendliness has been measured based on two areas: i) the OA publication area and ii) the use of a license in OA publications. The research uses data carpentry tools and techniques to collect and extract OA data from a variety of sources that are all available under the terms of the Open Database License (ODbL). To complete this extensive study for ranking the top 10 management institutions in India by their Open Access, a data carpentry tool called Open Refine and open access bibliographic/citation data sources like Unpaywall, Dimensions, are used.*

Keywords: Data carpentry, Open access, Open access friendliness, creative commons, Open Database License, Open Refine.

Introduction

Open Access (OA) is a notion that first appeared in 1991 and has since affected researchers all around the world. Budapest Open Access Initiatives (BOAI) defined open access as "...free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without-out financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself" (Chanet et al., 2002). A few scholars have tried to create indices of open access friendliness at the national, regional, and international levels, mostly based on OA share, publications in the repository, and OA colors. (Aguillo et al., 2010; Alperin et al., 2014; Gómez et al., 2009; Maddi, 2020).

By combining information from Web of Science, Unpaywall, and the Leiden ranking, a study team (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020) examined the OA levels at 963 universities around the world and discovered that British universities had the greatest percentage of OA (median=74%). In a groundbreaking study, Mukhopadhyay (2022) compared the open access friendliness of the major IITs

and discovered that the more recent IITs (IIT Gandhinagar) are more open access friendly than the more established ones, then after several scholars implement this on Indian intuitions.

The present study base on to measure the growth of OA publications in different OA routes in the last 5 years (2018-2023) in top ten public Universities and to show the use of CC licenses and growth of CC licenses in top 10 management institutions in the last 5 years.

The top 10 management institutions in India that have been ranked by the National Institutional Ranking Framework of India for 2024 in the overall category make up the sample for this research study (Table 1 lists the names and rankings of those universities).

Table 1: Ranking List of IIMs

Sl.No	NIRF Management Ranking 2024	Name of the institutions	State	Year of establishment.
1.	1	Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad	Gujarat	1961
2.	2	Indian Institute of Management Bangalore	Karnataka	1973
3.	3	Indian Institute of Management Kozhikode	Kerala	1997
4.	5	Indian Institute of Management Calcutta	West Bengal	1961
5.	6	Indian Institute of Management Mumbai	Maharashtra	1966
6.	7	Indian Institute of Management Lucknow	Uttar Pradesh	1984
7.	8	Indian Institute of Management Indore	Madhya Pradesh	1996
8.	9	XLRI - Xavier School of Management	Jharkhand	1949
9.	11	Management Development Institute Gurugram	Haryana	1973
10.	12	Indian Institute of Management Rohtak	Haryana	2010

Objectives

1. The primary objective of this study is to assess the increase of open access publications in the top ten during the last 5 years (2018-2023) using various open access pathways.
2. Another is to demonstrate the expansion of CC licenses and their use in the top 10 management institutions in India during the last 5 years.

Methodology

The present study has developed open access friendliness top 10 management institutions in India that have been ranked by the National Institutional Ranking Framework of India for 2024.

As many as 2,781 institutions participated in this ranking. The overall ranking is the combined list of top universities, engineering, management, pharmacy, college, medical, law, architecture, dental and research institutions.

Selection of Institutions

There are 876 management institutions National Institutional Ranking Framework of India for 2024 but only top 10 Specific management institutions are selected in the study.

Development of Primary Dataset

From September 07 to September 15, 2024, the primary data sets of publications from 10 management institutions were gathered from the Scopus bibliography and citation database. Primary publication (all documents) has been searched over the past five years (2018-2023) using institutions' affiliations Ids (eight digits), and has been downloaded year by year (like 2018) in 'CSV' formats. Through the use of appropriate scripts, the primary publishing data from five years has been combined into a single "CSV" file. The primary publications of universities and total publications over the most recent years (2018-2023) are displayed in Table 2. The development of secondary datasets relies heavily on the main data that has been released with a DOI. This study was retrieved from publications with a DOI and an open/close status.

Table 2: Primary dataset (arranged by the total number of publications in descending order)

Sl. No	Name of the institutions	Total publication (2018-2023)	Publication with DOI	Publication without DOI	NIRF Management Ranking 2024
1.	Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad	978	900	78	1
2.	Indian Institute of Management Lucknow	737	699	38	7
3.	Indian Institute of Management Bangalore	736	671	65	2
4.	Indian Institute of Management Indore	715	669	46	8
5.	Indian Institute of Management Kozhikode	617	580	37	3
6.	Indian Institute of Management Calcutta	574	488	86	5

Sl. No	Name of the institutions	Total publication (2018-2023)	Publication with DOI	Publication without DOI	NIRF Management Ranking 2024
7.	XLRI - Xavier School of Management	411	392	19	9
8.	Indian Institute of Management Rohtak	368	355	13	12
9.	Indian Institute of Management Mumbai	188	180	8	6
10.	Management Development Institute Gurugram	121	113	8	11
	Total	5445	5047	398	

Development of Secondary Dataset

Currently, 5445 DOI papers with open access status have been retrieved from the primary data collection, which is ready to combine the most recent 5 years' worth of data from a total of ten management institutions. More than 398 (7.3 %) papers from management institutions do not have a DOI.

Open Access Data: Unpaywall is a repository for open access bibliographic information (51,119,763+ records as of 14 September 2024 and Continuing). It lists 50,000 publishers with open access status and offers open access materials. Through REST/API requests, this enables open access to publication status. There is a daily cap of 100,000. Table 3 provides a description of the API structure and DOI response.

Table 3. Unpaywall - API calls and results

API call structures for Unpaywall	No. of queries sent	Responses received
<code>https://api.unpaywall.org/v2/" +value +""?email=arindamyoginath@gmail.com"</code>	5447	5047

Data Extraction

Data extraction is a crucial next stage in this process. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) formats are used by Unpaywall to give publications status. Open-access tool for data manipulation The General Refine Expression Language (GREL) of Openrefine was used to extract publishing status. Table 4 below provides a description of several GREL and outcomes.

Table 4. GREL- an example to extract data from Unpaywall datasets

Response from unpaywall in JSON	GREL for data extraction	Extracted Data
<pre>"genre": "journal-article", "is_paratext": false,"published_date": "2023- 05-11", "year": 2023, "journal_name": "Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology", "journal_issns": "2090-5920", "journal_issn_1": "1687-157X", "journal_is_oa": true, "journal_is_in_doaj": true, "publisher": "Springer Science and Business Media LLC", "is_oa": true, "oa_status": "gold", "has_repository_copy": true, "best_oa_location": {"updated": "2023-07- 11T16:35:36.472942", "url": "https://jgeb.springeropen.com/ counter/pdf/10.1186/s43141- 023-00506-9", "url_for_pdf": "https://jgeb.springeropen.com/ counter/pdf/10.1186/s43141- 023-00506-9", "url_for_landing_page": "https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141- 023-00506-9", "evidence": "oa journal (via doaj)", "license": "cc-by", "version": "publishedVersion", "host_type": "publisher", "is_best": true, "pmh_id": null, "endpoint_id": null, "repository_institution": null, "oa_date": "2023-05-11"}},</pre>	<pre>value.parseJson().is_oa value.parseJson().oa_status value.parseJson().oa_location[0] .license</pre>	<pre>TRUE GOLD CC-BY</pre>

Discussion and Findings

This section of the research describes the open-access contributions of the top ten public Universities that are ranked in the UGC-B overall ranking.

Generic Scenarios

Table 5: Colours of Open Access Licences

Sl. No	Name of Universities	Total open access documents in (2018-2023)	Bronze OA	Gold OA	Green OA	Hybrid OA
1.	Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad	273	44	103	71	55
2.	Indian Institute of Management Bangalore	194	35	69	57	33
3.	Indian Institute of Management Kozhikode	130	35	33	48	14
4.	Indian Institute of Management Calcutta	85	31	25	17	12
5.	Indian Institute of Management Mumbai	46	9	25	5	7
6.	Indian Institute of Management Lucknow	119	19	45	34	21
7.	Indian Institute of Management Indore	172	22	74	56	20
8.	XLRI - Xavier School of Management	75	16	27	22	10
9.	Management Development Institute Gurugram	27	3	15	6	3
10.	Indian Institute of Management Rohtak	73	14	33	15	11
	Total =	1194	228	449	2896	1800

Table 5 gives a systematic breakout of open access (OA) Publications by ten prime Indian management institutes in the course of 2018-2023. The data is segmented into four categories of OA: Some of the categories include; Bronze OA, Gold OA, Green OA, and Hybrid OA. This analysis will seek to establish the distribution of these OA categories among the institutions in question so as to get a feel of their publication habits and OA policies.

The table is organized into rows corresponding to individual universities and columns representing:

1. University Name: Identifies the producing institution in its case, with regards to the type of the Publication in question.
2. Total Open Access Documents: The total number of the publications in the form of OA documents to cover the time period of 2018 to 2023.
3. Bronze OA: OA documents where although the publisher gives a snapshot to 'No immediate access' documents are fully available via third party Proxies.
4. Gold OA: OA documents that are published in journal where content is made openly available with the intention of being used by consumers.
5. Green OA: that are deposited by authors in institutional or subject repositories as OA documents.
6. Hybrid OA: OA articles that appear in journals that have hybrid model of publishing, where one can find paid access as well as free access to articles.

Analysis of Data:

Total Open Access Documents

Total OA documents produced differ widely from one institution to another: ranging from 27 to MDI Gurugram to 273 in IIMA. This is due to the fact that these establishments are differently involved in open access publishing. As it can be observed IIM has the highest number of documents with 273 which may imply that the institute values and promotes open access publishing. Management Development Institute Gurugram has the fewest documents, which means that the institute may publish fewer OA articles or may be less involved in OA policies. Bronze OA bronze oa takes most of open access documents due to several reasons for many institutions. IIM Ahmedabad contributes the highest number of documents at the Bronze OA level, which suggests that a considerable portion of its OA publications is accessible only on the third-party websites.

On the other hand, some B-schools, including Management Development Institute Gurugram and Indian Institute of Management Mumbai had lower numbers in this category; 3 and 9 respectively, which may mean that they are not so dependent on, or easily found through third-party channels. Gold OA documents are fully OA immediately on publication and these documents often entail payment of fees for publishing. Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad leads in Gold OA with 103 documents which shows a good investment in contributing in fully open access journals. However, IIM Calcutta has the lowest number of Gold OA documents which is 25 and this could mean that IIM Calcutta publishes less frequently in Gold OA journals or uses the Gold OA method less frequently or maybe uses other forms of OA more frequently.

Green OA requires authors consciously depositing copies of their works in repositories which are usually free. Two Indian IIM institutions: Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad and Indian Institute of Management Bangalore are remarkably using institutional repositories for OA as evident by the significant number of green OA documents deposited (71 and 57 respectively). IIM Kozhikode and IIM Calcutta are found to have relatively lesser focus on Green OA with 48 and 17 articles present respectively.

Comparative Analysis

Ranking on all these parameters, IIM Ahmedabad known as Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad has emerged as the leader which depicts that it has a broader and integrated approach towards OA=Open Access.

Other OA domains also present robust performance on both Indian Institute of Management Bangalore and Indian Institute of Management Indore displays imposing research outputs towards openness. Some of the institutions such as Management Development Institute Gurugram and Indian Institute of Management Mumbai have comparatively lower overall numbers, which may indicate the lack of adequate interaction with OA publishing.

Table 6 Year wise distribution of OA Colours Growth

YEAR	TOTAL	CLOSE	OPEN	GREEN-OA	GOLD-OA	BRONZ E-OA	HYBRID -OA	%
2018	733	586	147	45	36	54	12	20.05
2019	751	584	167	44	65	46	12	22.23
2020	829	661	168	47	75	24	22	20.26
2021	911	709	202	70	84	24	24	22.17
2022	1053	817	236	72	86	28	50	22.41

YEAR	TOTAL	CLOSE	OPEN	GREEN-OA	GOLD-OA	BRONZE-OA	HYBRID-OA	%
2023	1168	894	274	53	103	52	66	23.45

This table indicates a positive trend towards open access publishing, with a steady increase in both the number and percentage of open access documents. This trend reflects the growing emphasis on accessibility and dissemination of academic research. The significant rise in Gold OA documents in recent years suggests a shift towards more immediate and accessible publishing models.

In comparison to the Green, Hybrid, and Bronze paths, the general trends of open access publications from 10 management institutions demonstrate that the Gold path of OA is continuously expanding during the years (2018-2023). The tabular data demonstrates the growth of open access publications at those ten public universities over a six-year period (20.26% in 2019 as the lowest to 23.45 % in 2023) in terms of percentage. Additionally, it demonstrates that the number of open access publications has increased by 03.19%.

Table 7 Years wise OA license type wise

Years	CC-BY	CC-BY-NC	CC-BY-NC-ND	CC-BY-NC-SA	CC-BY-ND	CC-BY-SA	OTHERS OA	BLANK
2018	15	10	27	1	0	0	22	72
2019	33	11	34	1	0	0	16	72
2020	54	13	30	1	0	0	16	54

Years	CC-BY	CC-BY-NC	CC-BY-NC-ND	CC-BY-NC-SA	CC-BY-ND	CC-BY-SA	OTHERS OA	BLANK
2021	62	12	33	2	1	0	20	72
2022	96	15	24	4	0	0	18	79
2023	96	20	52	2	0	0	15	89

Below is a tabular form showing how many LICENSES for Creative Commons have been used from the year 2018 and the following years up to 2023. Each of them refers to the certain level of openness and re-striction applied to the usage and distribution of creative production. The licenses are categorized as follows: The licenses are categorized as follows:

- CC-BY: Attribution
- CC-BY-NC: Attribution-Non-commercial
- CC-BY-NC-ND: Attribution-Non-commercial-No Derivatives
- CC-BY-NC-SA: Attribution-Non-Commercial-Share Alike
- CC-BY-ND: Attribution-No Derivatives
- CC-BY-SA: Attribution-Share Alike
- OTHERS: Other licenses which cannot be classified under previous categories
- CC-BY: Same as creative commons license enables the work to be used by others for distribution, remix, adaptation and building upon it, the number has risen from 15 in 2018 to 96 in 2023. This shows an increase of 540 percent over the six years which points to increased use of the most open license among the contributors to the dataset.
- CC-BY-NC: The amount of works includes this license rose and fell: in 2018 the number was 10, whereas in 2023 it reached the number of 20. It is noteworthy that CC-BY-NC is growing relatively slower compared to general CC-BY despite the general increase in both the number of licenses used and the popularity of licences with creative commons.
- CC-BY-NC-ND: This license has been constant in most of the years with a slight rise from 27 in 2018, 2019 to 52 in 2023. It shows a relatively slight increase in the desire for a license that restricts changes and purely business purposes.
- CC-BY-NC-SA: The count for this license has not dramatically increased: the minimum value was 2, and the maximum, 4 in 2022. One must admit that this license exhibits a stable demand for this combination of non-commercial use and share-alike terms.
- CC-BY-ND: It has increased from 0 to 1 between 2021 and 2022, but this category still remains negligible as compared to other categories.
- CC-BY-SA: The demand for licensing CC-BY-SA has always remained low and in the recent years; there has been only 20 works licensed in 2021 based on the chart below. These stable numbers indicate that there is little embracing of this more rigorous share-alike license.
- OTHERS: The figures of other licenses are slightly fluctuating, yet it is still quite a large portion of the sample, which ranges from 16 to 22 works per year.

Growing Openness: In particular, an analysis of licences granted in the field of creative works showed an increase in the quantity of CC-BY licenses, which indicates the increasing tendency in licensing towards openness and flexibility. This might have been facilitated by a new appreciation for open access to works in that the number of times the works get to be used may go up. **Stability in Restricted Licenses:** That the figures in the restricted licenses (including such licenses as CC-BY-NC, CC-BY-NC-ND, etc.) have not posted remarkable changes, it can be stated that, despite favoring open licensing most of the consumers still consider specific restrictions in commercial use and creation of derivatives.

Future Trends: Should the tendencies toward the increase in the usage of CC-BY be observed in the future, one could expect higher numbers of open licenses in the subsequent years resulting from the developing trends towards the openness of knowledge and sharing of creative content.

Conclusion

Overall, this research study utilized data carpentry tools and techniques to assess the open access friendliness of the top 10 Management Institution in India. The study focused on two main areas: OA publication and the use of licenses in OA publications. Data was collected from various sources, including Scopus, Unpaywall, and Dimensions, and data extraction was carried out using Open Refine.

This paper reveals the past five years' growth and trend of Open Access (OA) publications in the top 10 management institutions in India concentrating on Creative Commons (CC) licenses usage. This analysis is based on the data collected from the first-tier bibliographic databases and repositories focusing the transformation of OA publishing in top Indian management schools. According to the results, it is possible to identify the increased tendency in the implementation of OA practices with the involvement of top management institutions. Most importantly, the Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad has demonstrated a relatively high level of commitment to OA and, therefore, has submitted the highest number of documents in all the categories. It is this growth that mirrors an overall trend of advance in the expansion of Academic research accessibility and distribution.

Key Findings

1. **Growth in OA Publications:** It can be observed that the overall journal articles published under OA has gone up which signals a growing trend towards open access among Indian management institutions. The increase in the frequency of OA documents especially in Gold OA proves the trend of increased open and direct access to research outputs.
2. **CC Licenses Usage:** No doubt the application of CC licenses has grown over time especially the CC-BY license. This trend is indicative of the shift towards open licenses which enables virtually anybody to use and alter the creative content. On the other hand, licences that have more stringency in their use involve limitations like non-commercial use or no derivatives, for instance, CC-BY-NC and CC-BY-NC-ND have registered slower progress hence there may be a bit of truth to the aspect where institutions use filters and trade-offs to create balance between open access and certain limitations to be put on the works in question.
2. **Institutional Variability:** Based on the data analyzed there is a significant variation in the OA contributions among the institutions. Among the universities, the Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad exhibit the highest OA output along with the similar number of diverse licenses. For instances, the Management Development Institute Gurugram was found to have deposited fewer articles in OA and, therefore, was considered to engage in less OA practices.

3. Future Trends: The rise in the CC-BY license usage coupled with increased number of Gold OA publications provide a promising outlook in the direction to promote open and free access to research outputs. The increase of OA documents is expected to persist due to the increasing acceptance of the open access advocates and practice of Open Access on the part of institutions.

Overall, the present study reveals an emerging tendency of openness in the selected Management institutions of India, thereby attesting to the potential of open access publishing in these institutions. The data shows a year-on-year trend of more open licensing of journals and more institutions subscribing to the OA models of disseminating their research work. These trends indicate openness with global open access movements as well as opening up the possibilities of scholarly work in the continuously changing dynamics of academic publishing.

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